

smartVOTE

State of Electoral Disinformation in Spain and Portugal

November 2025

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Executive Summary

Executive Summary

This report provides a comparative state-of-the-art analysis of disinformation in Spain and Portugal, examining its systemic manifestations, underlying dynamics, and institutional responses, as well as its electoral implications. Both countries, while sharing a common Iberian context, present distinct patterns in terms of intensity, actors involved, and societal impact.

The findings underline structural vulnerabilities that make both democracies susceptible to manipulation, while also pointing to differences in scale, political salience, and regulatory development. Upon analysis, we identified a specific overarching feature, common to both countries -18-24's display remarkably different behaviors and perceptions compared to the rest of the population and this is especially true regarding younger men.

Below we list the key-take aways from this report, observing the Iberian landscape in terms of consistent patterns, country specific trends and, finally, a detailed look at the 18-24 demographic, where we list key data points which better illustrate the needs and expectations of this group.

Common Patterns at the Iberian scale

- **European Context and Exposure:** both Spain and Portugal are embedded in the wider European information environment, which exposes them to cross-border disinformation campaigns and narratives circulating through social media platforms. The porous nature of the online space means that narratives originating in other European countries or globally (e.g., Russian propaganda, pandemic-related conspiracy theories) circulate seamlessly across Iberia.
- **Platform Dependency:** citizens in both countries rely heavily on platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, and increasingly TikTok for news consumption. This dependency amplifies vulnerabilities to algorithmic amplification of misleading or polarising content. Messaging apps in particular represent a closed ecosystem where fact-checking and monitoring are limited.
- **Challenges of Media Literacy:** limited levels of digital literacy remain a structural challenge in both Spain and Portugal. Citizens often lack the tools to critically assess online information, increasing susceptibility to false or misleading claims. Public investment in media literacy initiatives has been modest, and fragmented across institutions.
- **Fact-Checking Ecosystem:** both countries have developed active fact-checking organisations (e.g., Maldita and Newtral in Spain, Polígrafo in Portugal), often integrated into wider European networks. They play a central role in debunking viral falsehoods, yet face resource limitations and difficulty countering the speed and scale of disinformation flows.
- **Weak Signals of Foreign Interference:** while no systematic large-scale campaigns directly targeting Spain or Portugal have been confirmed, there are weak signals of interference and opportunistic use of Iberian audiences by foreign actors. Both countries are therefore not insulated from global disinformation strategies.

Country specific trends and dynamics

- **Scale and Political Centrality:** Spain experiences a higher volume and political salience of disinformation. Polarisation, particularly around Catalonia, immigration, and electoral competition, fuels a fertile ground for disinformation actors. Portugal, by contrast, records lower levels of political polarisation, and disinformation remains a less central feature of political life.
- **Actors and Narratives:** In Spain, partisan actors and far-right movements actively produce and disseminate disinformation, exploiting identity-based and territorial fault lines. Narratives often focus on delegitimising institutions and fostering distrust. In Portugal, disinformation is less tied to mainstream political actors, and tends to revolve around global issues (e.g., health, climate, conspiracies) rather than domestic political conflicts.
- **Institutional Responses:** Spain has taken more visible steps in aligning with European Union initiatives on disinformation, including regulatory debates and parliamentary inquiries. Portugal's institutional response has been more reactive and less centralised, relying mainly on independent organisations and limited state engagement.
- **Media System Dynamics:** Spain's larger, more fragmented media landscape creates a fertile environment for competing narratives and polarised debates, amplifying the visibility of disinformation. Portugal's smaller and more concentrated media system provides some insulation, though economic fragility in the sector may pose risks in the medium term.

Younger Iberians and their relationship to news and disinformation

Spain

- Main news source: 18–24s lean much more toward social media than TV as their primary source (~41% social vs. 26% TV), while the overall adult population is more balanced across sources.
- Trust in news: Sharp generation gap. Only 19% of 18–24s say they trust “most news most of the time,” vs. roughly one-third in the full sample.
- Interest in news: Lower among youth (~34% interested) compared with about 52% in the overall population.
- News avoidance: Youth avoid more often (~43% among 18–24s) while overall avoidance is ~37%. Male–female differences among youth are small.
- Concern about online falsehoods: Lower for 18–24s (~63% concerned) than for the overall public (~70%).
- Topics where youth see more disinformation (self-reported, last week): 18–24s—especially young men—report higher exposure than the national average, notably on politics and COVID-19.

Portugal

- Main news source: Among 18–24s, TV and social media are neck-and-neck as the main source (≈30% TV vs. 31% social), unlike older groups where TV leads more clearly.
- Trust in news: No major youth gap—about 53% of 18–24s trust the news, close to the overall level (~56%).
- Interest in news: Lower among youth (≈32%) vs. ≈51% overall.
- News avoidance: Youth avoid less than the overall public (≈35% vs. ≈38% overall). There is a gender gap among youth: men avoid more (38%) than women (31%).
- Concern about online falsehoods: Lower among 18–24s (≈60%) than the overall public (≈72%).
- Topics where youth see more disinformation (self-reported, last week): 18–24s—especially young men—report relatively higher exposure on immigration, COVID-19, and cost of living than the national average.

Cross-cutting youth specifics (both countries)

- Algorithmic gateways & social feeds: 18–24s rely more on algorithmic gateways (social, search, video/podcasts) than older adults; within youth, young women are especially likely to cite social media as the main gateway (pattern seen in both countries).
- Interest vs. trust: Youth show lower interest than the overall population in both countries, but the trust gap is much larger in Spain than in Portugal (where youth trust remains relatively high).
- Self-reported exposure to disinformation: 18–24s—particularly men—more often say they've seen false or misleading content in the last week, with topic patterns differing by country (Spain: politics/COVID-19; Portugal: immigration/COVID-19/cost of living).
- Political interest by gender: Among 18–24s, men report notably higher interest in politics than women in both countries (Spain: 33% vs. 16%; Portugal: 28% vs. 15%).

Disinformation constitutes a shared democratic vulnerability in both Spain and Portugal, sustained by structural factors such as platform dependency, weak media literacy, and limited institutional capacity. Yet, the phenomenon is more acute in Spain, where disinformation intersects with high political polarisation and partisan mobilisation. Portugal faces fewer immediate risks, but the persistence of global conspiracy theories and limited investment in systemic countermeasures leave it vulnerable to future shocks.

A comparative view highlights the need for both countries to strengthen media literacy, invest in sustainable fact-checking infrastructures, and enhance coordination with European frameworks. Spain's experience demonstrates the destabilising effects of disinformation in a polarised environment, while Portugal illustrates the risks of underestimating structural vulnerabilities in a less polarised society.

1. Introduction

1. Introduction

1.1. Regarding SmartVote

SmartVote is an Iberian consortium led by Fundación Cibervoluntarios that aims to promote awareness on technology and critical media literacy skills as triggers to an informed political and electoral participation in the public space.

The project is especially focused on the issue of disinformation as a social, political, technological and communicational phenomenon which in the past few years has become more prevalent in Spain and Portugal. Disinformation phenomena are not new but are a staple of the contemporary political and informational sphere and are inherently multidimensional in its causes and consequences.

At the beginning of this 3 year project we published an overarching document¹ that aimed to settle the scope of our intervention. This effort, authored by 23 experts from all 6 partner institutions of the consortium, compiled information on all relevant conceptual dimensions of the project, from news habits to the perception of disinformation, of technology, politics and the state-of-the-art of what is being worked in Spain and Portugal in terms of media literacy policy and interventions.

While the core part of this report has been extracted from the original document, to be released as a dedicated independent publication on the State of electoral disinformation in Spain and Portugal, several changes have been made. We have delved deeper into the processes of growing polarisation in Spain, Portugal and the EU and have also introduced new graphical elements and discussion regarding the topic of trust in the news.

As explored in section 1.2. *Considering the Iberian context*, the multidimensional internal processes are remarkably different in the two countries and its reading is vital to understand the systemic intervention we aim to accomplish in SmartVote.

In several interactions with the public and experts the topic of trust is frequently mentioned, namely due to the considerable gap between the two countries. This curiosity is often motivated by the perception that Spain and Portugal are quite similar at a social, political and cultural level and as such there is no apparent reason for such discrepancy. Another frequent perception is that higher or lower perception are correlated with also higher or lower consumption of news sources.

¹ Paisana, M., Vasconcelos, A., Couraceiro, P., Caldeira Pais, P. M. P., Cardoso, G., Baldi, V., Barriuso Varela, O., Álvarez-Corona, E., Espiritusantu, O., Dinant, I., Magallon-Rosa, R., Fernández-Castrillo, C., Herrero Curiel, E., Molina Cañabate, J. P., Camacho, D., D'Antonio Maceiras, S., Huertas-Tato, J., Girón, A., Martín, A., ... Sales-Giménez, M. (2025). SmartVote - AI Initiative / Detection tools directory (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15305387>

Not only is that not necessarily true it is also rarely so: as we have seen throughout the history of news and journalism, brands and sources that are considered less trustworthy are often the ones who mobilise audiences the most, whereas legacy brands which are historically recognised as of impeccable reputation sometimes struggle to compete for attention with sources such as tabloid journalism or social media networks where, as we know, algorithms tend to amplify controversial and polarising content.

In any way, it should be mentioned that the trust placed by people on the news or in news media is not an indicator of the trustworthiness of said media, either due to the polarised nature of today's media ecosystem or due to the growing ignorance of the internal processes of journalism and fact-checking, with journalists and fact-checkers often being placed side-by-side with content creators who do not follow the same sort of ethical or deontological frameworks and guidelines.

The understanding trust in the news should be placed within the wider context of the contemporary struggle of journalism to legitimise itself, as our informational structures no longer determine that news brands are competing among themselves, but with everything else.

1.2. Considering the Iberian context

Spain and Portugal are considered relatively young democracies in the European context, due to their transitions from authoritarian regimes to democratic models of governance in the mid-1970's (Cerezales & Soriano, 2023, Badillo-Matos et al., 2023). The constitutional documents for both countries were drafted and approved in 1978 and 1976, respectively, and in both cases principles of press freedom and universal suffrage were enshrined, guaranteeing equal access to vote to all citizens in free and fair elections.

Notwithstanding the similarities in terms of how democracy was established (which, by the way, also extends to Southern European countries such as Greece), both countries developed into significantly different democracies in terms of their political and territorial organisation.

While Spain was established as a democracy in the form of a parliamentary monarchy, Portugal became a parliamentary republic, headed by an elected president.

The structure of both countries is a reflection of internal identity structures, which are much more pronounced in the Spanish case: the country operates in a quasi-federal model based in strong regional governments and, in the case of regions such as Catalonia and the Basque Country, very active nationalist movements, whereas Portugal is a unitary state, with very limited decentralisation and much more diluted regional identities and frameworks.

As such, regional and autonomic elections in both countries are very different in terms of their impacts and consequences. An additional layer of complexity and diversity is added in Spain by the strong identitarian fragmentation: In addition to Spanish as the official language throughout the territory, there are several co-official languages in different regions (Catalán, Galician, Basque, Valencian).

Table 1. Main aspects of political and territorial organisation in Spain and Portugal

Aspect	Spain	Portugal
State Model	Decentralized – Composed of Autonomous regions	Unitary – central government with 2 autonomous administrative regions
Subnational Units	17 Autonomous Regions + 2 Autonomous Cities	18 Districts (Distritos) and 2 Autonomous Regions (Azores, Madeira)
Degree of Autonomy	High – own parliaments, regional governments, broad autonomy in areas like health and education	Low to Moderate – Azores and Madeira have regional governments with legislative and political independence, mainland is centrally governed
Constitutional Recognition	Autonomous regions are constitutionally foreseen and protected (1978 Constitution)	Only Azores and Madeira have constitutionally established special status.

Source and Edition: OberCom / SmartVote.

Therefore, the level of autonomy allowed to Autonomous / Regional governments is very different. While all Spanish autonomous regions have their own governments and legislative parliaments, in the Portuguese case only Azores and Madeira have regional parliaments, with limited autonomy –the heads of the regional governments respond directly to an official appointed by the President of the Republic (Representative of the Republic for the Autonomous of Azores and Madeira– one appointee for each).

The differences in independence levels are quite clear when it comes to aspects such as fiscal policy, for example: in Spain fiscal autonomy is limited, except in some cases, like the Basque Country and Navarra, which have special tax regimes; and in Portugal it is very limited, with slight adaptations. Due to the different political and territorial structures, the amount of elections happening overtime are quite different and with higher impact for regional populations due to Spain’s decentralized nature.

Taking a closer look at recent years, and considering only nationwide elections, which normally happen every four years in both countries, we find that while Spain held three general elections (two in 2019 and one in 2023), Portugal held four general elections.

Over the past six years, elections in Portugal have become much more frequent due to rising political instability and the inability for elected parties to form stable governments. More recently, the rise of the right-wing populist party Chega has also significantly changed the distribution of power in the March 10th General Elections of 2024.

The two-party system (PS - Partido Socialista, and PSD - Partido Social Democrata, center-left and center-right, respectively) was disrupted in 2015 when, for the first time, the party that won the elections (PSD) was not able to form a government, and PS governed on the basis of a parliamentary agreement with political forces to its left, thus breaking the traditional arc of governance.

In 2019, new political forces entered the parliament - Livre, Iniciativa Liberal, and Chega, far-left, liberal-right and far-right, respectively - and the so-called Portuguese exceptionalism came to an end, with the election of a member of a populist right-wing party (Chega) to the parliament. Ever since, political instability in national and regional elections has led to successive elections (in the case of the 2019, 2022, 2024 and 2025 legislative elections), which have resulted both from the minority governments difficulties to approve their policies in the parliament, and the association of government members with judicial cases or questions about their ethical (mis)conduct.

In 2024, by electing 50 members in a 230-seat parliament, Chega has announced the end of bipartisanship in Portugal, increasing uncertainty about stable governance solutions in the future, and objectively becoming part of the equation for governability, even if at a speculative level, as Chega as not yet been part of any national government.

In Spain, the political system was also affected by the initial arrival of two new parties in the 2015 general elections (Ciudadanos and Podemos), which changed the traditional two-party system. In the new scenario, repeating elections became more common, due to the difficulty of forming parliamentary majorities.

Table 2. List of elections in Spain and Portugal, 2019 to 2027

	Spain	Portugal
2019	General elections- April 28th Regional elections: Aragón, Asturias, Canarias, Cantabria, Castilla y León, Castilla La Mancha, Extremadura, Baleares, Madrid, Murcia, Navarra, La Rioja - April 28th European elections - May 26th Regional elections: Aragón, Madrid, Ceuta, Melilla - May 26th Municipal elections -May 26th General elections - November 10th	European elections - May 25th Regional elections (Madeira) September 22nd General elections - October 6th
2020	Regional elections: Euskadi - July 12nd	Regional elections (Azores) October 25th
2021	Regional elections: Cataluña February 14th Regional elections: Madrid - May 4th	Presidential elections - January 24th Municipal / Local elections - September 26th
2022	Regional elections: Castilla y León - February 13th Regional elections: Andalucía - June 19th	General elections - January 30th
2023	Regional elections: Aragón, Asturias, Baleares, Canarias, Cantabria, Castilla La Mancha, Extremadura, La Rioja, Madrid, Murcia, Navarra, Valencia, Ceuta and Melilla - May 28 Municipal elections - May 28th General slections - July 23	Regional elections (Madeira) September 24th
2024	Regional elections: Galicia - February 18th Regional elections: Euskadi - April 21st Regional elections: Cataluña - May 12th European elections - June 9	Regional elections (Azores) - February 4th General elections - March 10th Regional elections (Madeira) May 26th European elections - June 9
2025	None (at the date of publication of this report)	General elections - May 18th Municipal / Local elections - October 12th
2026	Regional elections: Andalucía, Castilla y León*	Presidential elections - January 18th
2027	Regional and local elections. * General elections.*	None (at the date of publication of this report)

Source and Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. * Election date to be determined.

Otherwise, the turning point in terms of disinformation began with the 2018 Andalusian elections. On election night, December 2, turnout radically changed the Andalusian political landscape. For the second time since 1982, turnout in the Andalusian Parliament elections fell below 60%. The PSOE (Spanish Socialist Workers' Party) recorded its worst result in a regional election in this region, surpassing the million-vote barrier by just 9,000 votes.

Meanwhile, the Popular Party (PP) got 749,000 votes; Ciudadanos got 660,000; Adelante Andalucía got 584,000; and Vox, the big surprise, got 396,000. The combined PP, Ciudadanos, and Vox achieved an absolute majority in the Andalusian Parliament, and the PSOE lost the Andalusian government after 37 years (Magallón-Rosa et al, 2019).

Although each electoral process has its own dynamics linked to current events and current debate topics, electoral disinformation narratives are increasingly global and they adapt themselves to different elections, combining local stories and protagonists.

From this point of view, there are several factors that explain the relevance that electoral campaigns have acquired, but the most important is the strategic culmination of permanent campaigns around a final moment of emotional saturation, the voting decision (Magallón-Rosa, 2024).

Furthermore, the Spanish general elections of April 28, 2019 –which preceded the European elections by a month– seem to be a worthy case regarding disinformation evolution, given that they were held in a climate of maximum alertness regarding the potential persuasiveness of false information (Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020).

Overall, Spain displays higher levels of political polarisation, magnified by social media, affecting electoral disinformation and fostering negative behaviors towards news, whereas Portugal, while less polarised, also shows increasing saturation, selective exposure and news avoidance, particularly among younger people (Badillo-Matos et al., 2023, Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024, Cardoso et al., 2024).

Longitudinally and looking specifically at the past 24 years, Spain has always displayed higher levels of political polarisation than Portugal and both displayed lower figures than the EU as a whole. However, from 2008 to 2011 onwards we witness a rise in political polarisation in Spain, likely due to the 2008–2011 financial crisis. This polarisation met EU levels around 2012 and remained stable up until 2019, when Spain accompanies wider polarisation felt across Europe (Coppedge et al. 2025).

It should be noted that the 2011 – 2019 period saw significant changes in the Spanish political landscape, with the creation of new political parties at both the extremes of the spectrum –Vox in 2013 and Podemos in 2014. While political polarisation cannot be directly attributed to the creation of these parties, their creation and growing electoral relevance is itself a reflection of a change and diversification of opinions in the country

Figure 1. Political polarisation in the European Union, Spain and Portugal, 2000 to 2024

Source: Coppedge et al. (2025). Varieties of Democracy Project (V-Dem). Edition: OberCom / SmartVote.

In Portugal, political polarisation levels remained stable and low ever since the beginning of the millenium, starting to rise around 2019 / 2020 and almost matching polarisation levels in the EU and Spain in 2024. The creation of far-right populist party Chega in 2019, the saturation with the long standing rule of Partido Socialista (center / center left) and the pandemic which started in 2020 may play a considerable role in this new stage of the country's evolution in terms of political polarisation.

Negative behaviors towards politics, elections, and participation are also common among young people in both countries, with voter turnout being lower in this demographic. In the 2009 European elections in Spain, approximately 65% of young people abstained from voting (Bouza, 2014) although in other instances spaniards below 25 have been known to mobilise in particularly sensitive moments - in the 2019 European elections voter turnout increased by 14 pp. compared to previous elections (European Parliament, 2022).

In Portugal, researchers highlight that absenteeism is becoming a habit among young people below 35, in particular in the 18-24 demographic (Durães, 2024), and that extremist parties on the left and right are the only ones able to mobilise young or inactive voters. While this trend may be identified in both countries, in Spain there have been significant shifts among the Spanish youth, with rising antifeminism speech and nostalgia for authoritarianism (Jones, 2025).

In both countries, and despite above and aforementioned differences, factors influencing youth electoral participation can be summed in: the feeling that politics does not represent their interests, decreased interest in politics at all, economic insecurity, unemployment and low job security than previous generations, and differences in territorial perceived identity (much more pronounced in Spain, where regional identity often shadows national and European identity).

Both countries have gone and are going through drastic digitalisation via platformisation in recent years. Portuguese people consecutively display high levels of trust in news but trust in news rates drop considerably in digital environments, and Spanish media operate in a more polarised environment, with growing presence of partisan digital ecosystems. Albeit less polarised, and with more moderate political discourse, there is increased concern regarding echo-chambers associated with the rise of far-right political relevance.

Considering the response to disinformation at a governmental and political level, Spain has developed a more solid response structure, like the Forum Against Disinformation Campaigns, an interministerial working group in alignment with European security strategies (Vicente, 2023).² Portugal, on the other hand, has taken a softer approach based on the guarantee of rights and freedoms with a strong emphasis on freedom of expression with less centralised actions against disinformation (Assembleia da República, 2021, Pardal & Narciso, 2023).

These ongoing dynamics happen in a very specific context in 2025, with heightened political shifts at a global level and the development of AI at a rapid pace, with fears of it being used as a disinformation amplifier, with higher potential for microtargeting voters, a regulatory framework that is still lacking, and a media ecosystem still learning to maximise the opportunities of AI in fact-checking and content moderation.

² See: <https://www.dsn.gob.es/foro-desinfo>

2. State of electoral disinformation in Spain and Portugal

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2.1. Gauging the relationship to news, political mobilization and disinformation

2.1.1. Sources of news and political information

In Spain, social media is the top source for information on political and social issues (42%) with TV running a close second (39%). About one in four respondents access news via online media and / or news platforms (26%), friends, family or colleagues (25%) and video platforms (European Parliament, 2025). While data for Spain follows a closer pattern to the one displayed by other Europeans, prioritizing social media over TV (49% over 44%). Flash Eurobarometer data for Portugal points in the same direction as other sources, such as the Digital News Report, with TV prevailing over social media by 13 pp. –53% against 40% (European Parliament, 2025).

Figure 2. Main sources for news, Spain and Portugal, 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024 Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries.

Digital News Report data also points towards these trends although with added nuance (Figure 1). In the case of Portugal, the proportion of 18-24's who rely primarily on TV for news is about the same as those who prefer social media (30% and 31%, respectively) while in the case of Spain the differences are considerable, of 41% against 26%, as seen in Figure 1 (Cardoso, et al., 2024, Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024).

In line with the general trends regarding news sources, the majority of young people (56%) use social media to stay informed about the European Union, specifically, although about half the sample of the Youth and Democracy report also use TV to stay on top of EU related news (European Commission, 2024). Interestingly, there is also a significant proportion of people (33%) using either online media, podcasts and / or news platforms, which suggests that this particular demographic resorts to multiple sources to stay up-to-date in regards to Europe related news.

Although there are methodological aspects to consider, such as the difference in age of analyzed respondents (Flash Eurobarometer reports covers 16-30's and DNR 18-24's) or the difference in questioning (first asks about what sources people use, the second one asks respondents to point out the main one), the Digital News Report data allows for a slightly more detailed view of the 18-24 age bracket.

Spanish young women are much more likely to use social media over TV than the general sample or than men – 47% use mainly social media against 21% who prefer TV. In the Portuguese case, it is the male 18-24 bracket that stands out, as seen in the general sample, young men prefer TV over social media. In Portugal's case, despite the higher adoption rates of social media in general and for news by younger people, the preference for TV is the same as that identified among older individuals (Cardoso et al., 2024).

Access to digital news in both countries is different in some aspects (Figure 2, next page). Direct access to news websites is at an all-time low, with only 15% and 16% of access to online news in Spain and Portugal happening directly. The importance of search also appears to be similar, with about one third of accesses in Spain, and slightly less in Portugal, happening via search engines (either by searching for a brand or a keyword associated with the news) (Cardoso et al., 2024, Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024).

However, we do find some differences when it comes to social media, which is more prevalent in Spain (28% of accesses) than in Portugal (20%). The Portuguese have more fragmented habits in this instance, opting in larger proportion to other forms of access to digital news content such as e-mail newsletters (9% vs. 5% in Spain) or mobile alerts (17% against 8%, respectively).

Figure 3. Main gateway to online news, Spain and Portugal, 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries.

Looking at the habits of 18-24's in both countries, it is visible that younger women are much keener on social media for news (44%) than men (29%), the latter preferring either search entries or direct access (35% and 13%, against 22% and 10% in women).

Differences in the proportion between young women and men using social media as the main gateway for news are as pronounced in Portugal as in Spain (35% and 44%, respectively).

As for the fragmentation among lateral forms of access, we find that this is truer in younger men than women, as male 18-24's are more likely to access news using e-mail newsletters or mobile alerts (10% and 14% against 4% and 9%). (Cardoso et al., 2024, Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024).

Figure 4. Use of algorithmic tools as the main gateway to news, Spain and Portugal, 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries.

Looking at an aggregation of all algorithmic tools which may be used to access online news, it is visible that these tools are more common in Spain than in Portugal and, also, that 18-24's are more likely to rely on these than the overall population.

However, this is particularly true when it comes to young women, who rely more on gateways such as social media for news gathering than men –44% against 29% in Spain and 35% against 24% in Portugal.

The composition of social media diets is also distinct in both countries, notwithstanding the fact that both the Spanish and Portuguese societies are pronouncedly multi-network when it comes to using social media as a way of accessing news.

Figure 5. Social Media usage for news, 18–24's, Spain and Portugal, 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries.

Instagram is now the most common source of news regarding political and social issues (47%) followed by TikTok (39%) and YouTube (37%) in Europe. X and WhatsApp are used by lower proportions of young people – 21% and 16% (European Parliament, 2024).

Other research covering Portugal suggests a higher prevalence of Instagram as well, but of YouTube and X ranking considerably lower. Data for Spain shows a much more fragmented social media landscape among young people, with Instagram, X, and YouTube having similar weight in news consumption.

2.1.2. Trust, interest and avoidance

Analyzed in parallel, data on trust, interest in news, and news avoidance for Spain and Portugal highlight both similarities and differences. When it comes to the objective evaluation of the state of the information and journalistic ecosystem, Portugal ranks historically high in the Press Freedom Index (6th out of 180 countries), whereas Spain is ranked 30th, due to the contamination of media environments by political polarisation and lower trust in journalism. Portugal, on the other hand, is less polarized, but journalists and media brands face economic, legal, and security challenges (Reporters Without Borders, 2024).

Figure 6. Trust in news in general, Spain and Portugal, 2015 to 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who agree or totally agree with the statement "I think you can trust most news most of the time".

Digital News Report data underlines the stark difference between both countries, trust-wise. 56% of Portuguese people say they trust the news, compared to a third of the Spanish respondents in the same report (Cardoso et al., 2024, Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024). The trust rate for Spain fell considerably from the 51% reported in 2017. As for Portugal, over the past ten years they have witnessed a 10 pp. decline from the 66% in 2015.

Figure 7. Net trust, Global (48 country comparison), 2024

Source: Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2024, Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. Country samples n=2000. Note: Net trust is the difference between the % of people who claim to trust the news in general and the % of people who claim to distrust the news. This difference is presented in percentage points.

In the global outlook, the iberian contrast in terms of trust in news is even more evident. Considering net trust, i.e., the proportion of citizens who say they trust the news in relation to the ones who do not, the portuguese situation is remarkably positive by comparison with Spain.

Portugal ranks 6th worldwide in terms of the largest positive difference in terms of net trust, meaning that it is a country where the number of people who trust the news far outweighs the number of people who do not, close to countries such as Finland, Hong Kong or Denmark.

By contrast, Spain is the 11th country out of 48, and one of 14 countries with negative net trust. These situation in these nations is particularly concerning as the structurally low trust is often motivated by political or social polarisation, economic uncertainty and or other sorts of divisional feelings which are extended to the generality of the population rather than one or other specific demograhic group.

Irregardless of similar proportions in terms of net trust, the perception of media has to be analysed on a case-by-case basis. In the spanish case, while distrust outweighs trust in across all age groups, it is much more prevalent among young people – a trend that is often attributed to the fact that younger citizens rely more on digital platforms to get their news, a context in which disinformation is more prevalent and polarisation more noticeable.

It should, however, be noticed that unlike Portugal, where these rates are practically the same, in Spain citizens place much more trust on the news they consume than in the news in general -in 2024, 4 out of 10 spaniards say they trust the news they consume opposed to the already mentioned 33% who say they trust news in general. Novoa-Jaso et al. (2024) argue that the issue of trust in the news in Spain has to be looked at through the lens of “selective trust”, meaning that news consumers feel that they are more immune in their own personal news environment than in relation to the ecosystem as a whole.

On the other hand, this discrepancy can also be attributed to higher critical skills by citizens, which results in the choice of more trustworthy sources. In any case, this higher reliance on sources that the person interacts with may also signify the existance of echo-chambers and of the circulation of citizens in environments which tend to confirm previously hel opinions and biases.

Globally, trust figures have been known to vary widely and for different reasons, although one overall trend is that since 2015 –especially in the aftermath of Brexit and the 2016 US presidential election– trust has become a much more complex and nuanced indicator to read and interpret, as it has become much more volatile to the overlap with fields such as politics, economics and with disinformation topics related to the pandemic or the Ukraine War.

Figure 8. Trust in news in general – 18 to 24, Spain and Portugal, 2015 to 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who agree or totally agree with the statement "I think you can trust most news most of the time".

Focusing attention on the 18-24's demographic, and as mentioned above, the picture is bleak for Spain, as only one-fifth of these respondents (19%) claim to trust the news, while in Portugal trust rates are much higher and similar between the overall population and younger citizens (53%).

A closer look at the aftermath of the pandemic, 2021 to 2024, shows diverging trends among Spanish and Portuguese 18-24's: whereas trust levels have been stable /slightly rising in Portugal, in Spain trust figures have dropped 13 pp. since 2022. The country ranks particularly low in the international outlook, and the authors of the Digital News Report 2024 state that Spain is one of 15 countries in 47 with negative net trust, i.e., the proportion of people distrusting the news is 6 pp. higher than the proportion of people who trust. Among 18-24's this net trust is even worse, with 56% saying that you cannot trust most news most of the time –a difference of 37 pp. (Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024).

Figura 9. Trust by age group, Spain and Portugal, 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who agree or totally agree with the statement "I think you can trust most news most of the time". Lines

In Portugal trust rates tend to be slightly more stable across ages, but there appears to be a slight division between those under and those above 44 / 45 years old, the latter displaying higher trust levels across all age groups. In Spain, Novoa-Jaso et al. (2024) identify a direct correlation between age and trust, suggesting that a lower exposure to overloaded and saturated digital news environments may explain the more positive perception among those above 55 years old.

The authors of the Digital News Report España 2024 argue that digital-born Spaniards have been socialized into a much more fragmented and polarised media ecosystem, having developed a higher critical sense and some cynicism regarding legacy media sources and the news as a whole.

Figure 10. Interest in news, Spain and Portugal, 2015 to 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who say they are extremely and very interested in news.

Considering the interest in news, rates are quite similar for both countries in 2024, with about half of the population declaring to be interested in news (52% for Spain and 51% for Portugal). However, longitudinal analysis points out that interest has dipped in both countries compared to 2015, when more than 8 out of 10 Spanish and 7 out of 10 Portuguese respondents claimed to trust news —85% and 70%, respectively, meaning a 33 pp. and a 19 pp. drop in each country, also respectively.

Figure 11. Interest in news - 18 to 24, Spain and Portugal, 2015 to 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who say they are extremely and very interested in news.

The 18-24 age group displays considerably lower interest rates compared to the national samples for both countries, with about one-third of younger individuals claiming to be interested in news (34% for Spain and 32% for Portugal). As in the overall sample, Spanish and Portuguese 18-24's display very close interest levels, and in both cases, there is a considerable dip in interest in the aftermath of the pandemic.

News avoidance has been on the rise in several European countries, with different societies displaying diverging avoidance patterns: countries in Eastern Europe are more likely to avoid news altogether because of the prevalence of Ukraine war-related content, and the geographical proximity to the area where the conflict is taking place.

Figure 12. News avoiders, Spain and Portugal, 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who often / sometimes avoid the news.

Avoidance patterns in Western Europe tend to be more selective, with people opting to spend less time with news or avoiding specific topics such as pandemic related information and politics (particularly around electoral when people tend to become more saturated with the monothematic coverage) (Newman et al., 2023, Newman et al., 2024).

Avoidance rates for Spain and Portugal are quite close, at 37% and 38%, respectively, but looking at the 18-24 demographic, we come across different scenarios: younger news users in Spain are more likely to avoid news more often (43%) while in Portugal it's the exact opposite (35%). Adding the gender variable to the analysis, it is visible that in the case of Spain, men and women aged 18 to 24 avoid news in about the same proportion, whereas in Portugal, men are considerably more likely to display avoidance behaviors (38% compared to 31% of women).

2.1.3. Perceptions and attitudes towards disinformation

Perceptions and attitudes towards disinformation are particularly complex to gauge, as they are highly volatile and permeable to subjective interpretations and the differences between knowledge systems, beliefs, and perceptions of wider social and political phenomena. As such, country comparisons based on perceived disinformation, its volume, range, and topics must always be equated with the specific national context. As mentioned in the introduction, in the Iberian case, there are stark differences in terms of politics, territorial organization, and administration, and also at a cultural, social and historical level.

Figure 13. Concern about what is real or fake online, Portugal and Spain, 2020 to 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who strongly agree or tend to agree that they are concerned about what is real and what is fake on the internet.

Despite these differences, a similar trend is observed on the perception of disinformation measured by the concern about online disinformation, with the wider national samples revealing higher concern compared to their younger subsets of respondents: about 7 out of 10 people in Spain and Portugal (70% and 72%) are concerned about what is real and fake online whereas concern rates for 18-24's is at 63% and 60%, respectively. European Commission data (2018) mentions that about 80% of Spaniards often find news that distorts reality or is false, and the same proportion says that disinformation is a problem in Spain, and 83% believe disinformation is a problem for democracy. As for Portugal, 75% claim to encounter disinformation frequently, a proportion similar to the one in Digital News Report data.

Figure 14. Concern about what is real or fake online, 18-24, Portugal and Spain, 2020 to 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who strongly agree or tend to agree that they are concerned about what is real and what is fake on the internet.

Concern about disinformation is lower among younger individuals in both countries, and younger people also tend to state, in a higher proportion, to not be worried about online disinformation. Concern also tends to be higher among those with higher education and wages. Despite the weight of sociodemographic factors in explaining concern about disinformation, a set of other factors appears to be determinant: high interest and high trust in news, especially when combined, are among the stronger predictors of awareness regarding disinformation (Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024, Cardoso et al., 2024).

2.1.4. Activism and mobilisation

Unlike most EU countries, Spanish and Portuguese young people value freedom of speech and thought higher than the protection of human rights, democracy, and peace – EU 41% vs. 45%, Spain 46% vs. 44%, and Portugal 49% vs. 51%. European young women are more likely than their male counterparts to value the protection of human rights, democracy and peace, gender equality, tolerance and respect for diversity in society, the fight against discrimination, and the protection of minorities (European Parliament, 2025).

Although young people are very active in participating in a wide range of organizations, participation in societal change actions is slightly lower – 64% have engaged in activities in at least one organization, whereas 48% have mobilized in actions to change society. These include signing petitions, participating in rallies, or contacting politicians (European Commission, 2024). European Parliament data (2025) also highlights the importance of human rights and climate change as triggers for activism among younger Europeans.

Although these rank close to issues such as health/well-being or rights equality in gender, race or sexuality highlighting the fragmented concerns across different topics, complementary European Commission data (2024) suggests that young people are also concerned about topics such as inflation, the economy (namely employment) and social protection, even if these particular issues are not sufficient to trigger effective action and social or political participation.

In Spain and Portugal, data on young activism follows EU trends closely, both in terms of the size of said participation and the causes which motivate it. However, there are slight differences between both: while Portugal stands closer to the EU averages, in Spain the issues related to equality, either of gender, race or sexuality, are at the top of mind among the Spanish youth, outranking themes such as human rights or climate change – close to one in every four young people in Spain claim to be motivated to action by equalitarian causes (38%), about the same proportion in Portugal are mobilized by human rights (39%).

It should be noticed that despite having their social and political interests divided among several issues, some topics may be more influential in shaping youth activism and/or political participation such as mental health, an issue that has personally impacted more than 46% of young people in the recent past (European Commission, 2024), and public debate and attention is also growing.

The dynamics surrounding overall interest in politics point towards considerably higher interest in young 18 to 24 men compared to the overall age group and women: in Spain, 33% of young men claim to be interested in politics, against 16% of women, and in Portugal we find a similar situation, in proportions of 28% and 15%, respectively.

Figure 15. Interest in politics, Spain and Portugal, 2015 to 2024

Source: Digital News Report España 2024, Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. n≈2000 in both countries. Note: % values represent people who say they are extremely and very interested in politics.

Historical analysis of voter turnout suggests that in most countries women have lower voter turnout compared to men (Portugal is a particularly representative case for this), even though in some specific cases, such as Sweden in particular, and Scandinavia in general, women tend to largely outperform men in electoral turnout (Rapp & Schweizer, 2024).

As the influence of identity and belonging becomes more complex, so does the ability to identify the motivations for mobilization and voting, as these depend not only on personal characteristics but also on social, cultural, historical, and economic factors that influence context and are changed by it.

For instance, despite being recognizably favorable towards the European Union (64% say they are), 32% of young people argue that despite being favorable, they do not agree with the way Europe works presently, and evidence suggests that national and country identity remains the key factor for personal attachment (32%), and European identity are less strong in these terms (15% say they are attached to Europe).

Geographical and political aspects also matter. Despite having joined the European Union at the same time, in 1986, and having about the same proportion of young people declaring to feel attached to Europe – 14% in Spain and 15% in Portugal – the feeling of belonging to the local and regional community is much higher in Spain (26% against 18%) and the attachment to national identity stronger in Portugal (37% compared to 28%).

Regardless of whatever aspects lead to mobilization, the most common forms of participation are voting in any election (39%), followed by creating or signing petitions (on paper or online) (26%). Actions such as volunteering for a charity or campaign, sharing your opinion online, or boycotting certain products are less common, mentioned by about 1 in every 5 individuals.

A percentage of 15% are total absentees, claiming to not engage in any way with any of the activities, and specific data on absenteeism during the June 2024 European election shows that having other commitments is the most common reason to have skipped the vote (16%), followed by the lack of information to support a choice (16%) and the absence of a candidate that reflects their views (15%). Also, 15% display general distrust or dissatisfaction with politicians and politics (European Parliament, 2024).

2.2. Disinformation narratives in Portuguese and Spanish elections

The topic of disinformation in election campaigns has become increasingly important, especially after the 2016 presidential election in the United States (Faris et al., 2017), where it was suspected that foreign disinformation may have influenced the election result (Bovet & Makse, 2019). Since 2016, disinformation in elections has been described as a recurring phenomenon (Bader, 2018), with studies pointing to incidents in the Brexit referendum (Cervi & Carrillo-Andrade, 2019), during the Covid-19 pandemic (European Commission, 2020), but also in various elections in several European countries, including the UK (Vaccari et al., 2023), Italy (Pierrri et al., 2020) France (Ferrara, 2017), Germany (Zimmermann & Kohring, 2020) and also Spain (Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020; Cano-Óron et al., 2021; Maldita, 2023) and Portugal (Cardoso et al., 2020; Baptista & Gradim, 2022; Casquinho et al., 2024a; Casquinho et al., 2024b).

In an electoral context, disinformation campaigns usually involve the repetition of false information, the manipulation of news, studies, and polls, as well as the general discrediting of political opponents (Bader, 2018; Bendiek & Schulze, 2019). When disinformation directly targets political candidates, it often involves fabricated statements, personal relationships, and policies, while stories about parties tend to revolve around proposals, secret alliances, and supposed beneficiaries of policies (Magallón-Rosa et al., 2019). As Paniagua-Rojano et al. (2020) note, stories about electoral disinformation are sometimes reproduced across multiple elections and in different countries.

Contextually, as Zimmermann & Kohring (2020) have shown, the less people trust the news media and politics in election campaigns, the more they tend to believe in disinformative content. It has also been observed that receiving campaign news from professional news organizations correlates with the ability to distinguish true from false information (Vaccari et al., 2023). Overall, it is important to emphasize the danger that disinformation can have in elections by influencing results, but also by inflicting several structural effects, such as "(...) the polarisation of society or distrust in and delegitimization of democratic processes and institutions." (Departamento de Seguridad Nacional, 2022, pp.5-6.)

From a conceptual point of view, the study of disinformation in election campaigns requires a clear definition of disinformation. In this report, we follow the definition proposed by the European Union's High-Level Group of Experts (HLEG), which defines disinformation as "the creation, presentation and dissemination of verifiably false or misleading information for the purposes of economic gain or intentionally deceiving the public, and which may cause public harm".

Despite the general adaptability of the definition proposed by the HLEG, we believe it is important to also consider the categorization proposed by Wardle and Derakhshan (2017), which specifies that misinformation is shared without the intention to cause harm; disinformation is deliberately created and disseminated with the intention to deceive; and malinformation is based on reality but decontextualized to cause harm.

Furthermore, in this report, we tend to avoid terms such as "fake news" as they are generally ambiguous and lack conceptual development. Many authors have approached this term (Tandoc et al., 2018; Coady, 2019; Dentith, 2017; Gelfert, 2018; Lilleker, 2017; Meinert et al., 2018) and generally conclude that it is somewhat convoluted, used as a "catch-all term" (Lilleker, 2017) and often employed by political actors and their supporters as a means to suppress opinions that contradict them and to degrade their opposition, as well as media organizations.

As mentioned in the introduction to this report, this chapter will mainly focus on electoral disinformation studies conducted online. Overall, interest in social media, particularly Twitter/X, in the analysis of political campaigns increased after the Obama campaign in the 2008 presidential election in the United States, which was recognized for its success in mobilizing voters (Maarek, 2014). Despite the possibilities of social media, it is often observed that political representatives do not employ these platforms to interact directly with their supporters but rather pursue a general informational strategy (López-García et al., 2016; Waisbord & Amado, 2017; Magallón-Rosa et al., 2019). Regardless of this, the online activities of politicians during political campaigns generally increase as the campaign draws to a close (Maarek, 2014; López-García et al., 2016).

Studies on disinformation on the Internet during elections have shown that identifying false narratives is not always an easy process. As Casquinho et al. (2024a) note, the distinction between what is disinformation and merely freedom of expression can be difficult to access and may be conditioned by an individual's political preference. Additionally, Cano-Óron et al. (2021) conclude that distinguishing between advertising, propaganda, and disinformation on social media can be a difficult exercise.

Previously, it has been suggested that disinformation, especially in relation to politics, spreads more quickly on social media (Vosoughi et al., 2018) and that these platforms can contribute to the development of echo chambers and filter bubbles (Colleoni et al., 2014; Saurwein & Spencer-Smith, 2021). Furthermore, the use of social media platforms as a source of political campaign news seems to be related to the difficulty of distinguishing between true and false information (Vaccari et al., 2023). This conjecture makes social media platforms a fundamental object of study to understand and prevent the spread of disinformation, especially during elections.

In the following subsections, we will present different studies that analyze disinformation in elections in the Portuguese context and then in the Spanish context. After these first separate analyses, we will offer a comparative perspective to understand the differences and similarities regarding electoral disinformation in both countries.

2.2.1. Spain

In Spain, the number of studies on elections in social media has increased since the 2010's, with Twitter in particular being a frequent object of study because of the former access to Twitter Api (Rivas-de-Roca et al., 2022). As far as political communication on social media during elections is concerned, we mainly find studies on general elections, but also some on regional elections and municipal elections. Overall, European elections tend to be a less prominent object of study (Rivas-de-Roca et al., 2022).

In the 2019 elections, the main Spanish fact-checkers, Maldita and Newtral, established themselves as sources for verifying claims made by the candidates and as agents against rumors and hoaxes that spread on social media during the campaign. Otherwise, it is measurable that, in terms of verifications carried out by fact-checking organizations, the number of hoaxes and misinformation narratives circulating in the July 2023 general elections was much higher than in the 2019 elections.

According to Maldita (2023), Spain has a history of disinformation during electoral seasons, particularly targeting the integrity of elections. Following a recommendation of the EU, in 2020, the Spanish Department of National Security set up a group of experts from civil society to work with representatives of public administration to combat and prevent disinformation, in order to ensure the protection and preservation of democratic values (Departamento de Seguridad Nacional, 2022). Overall, since around 2015, there has been an increase in studies that approached disinformation online (Rivas-de-Roca et al., 2022), especially during general elections (Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020; Cano-Óron et al., 2021; Maldita, 2023).

Studies on online political communication have shown that the volume of publications by both political and media agents tends to increase over the course of the election campaign, especially in the later stages. This applies to both general elections (López-García et al., 2016; Maldita, 2023) and regional elections (Magallón-Rosa et al., 2019).

Television debates were also identified as a focus of discussion on Twitter in various elections (Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020; Magallón-Rosa et al., 2019; Marcos-García, 2016; Rivas-de-Roca, 2021; Córdoba-Cabús et al., 2021). In fact, in the 2021 regional elections in Madrid, media coverage on Twitter focused mainly on campaign events and electoral debates (Córdoba-Cabús et al., 2021).

As Marcos-García (2016) mentions, this reinforces the idea of convergence between media. However, in Rivas-de-Roca's study on the regional elections in Galicia in 2020, the author highlights that the issues raised online by politicians do not always coincide with the issues raised in televised debates. Furthermore, despite the importance of televised debates, Magallón-Rosa et al. (2019) observed that discussions intensified even more on election day.

Zamora-Medina & Zurutuza-Muñoz argued in 2014 that "(...) Spanish politicians have not yet understood that Twitter/X is a tool focused on the candidate as a person rather than as part of a political institution". However, it is important to understand that, as mentioned by López-García et al. (2016), there tends to be a difference between the way emerging and established parties use social media.

As the authors pointed out during the 2015 general election, Podemos and its then leader Pablo Iglesias took a more conversational and interactive approach, in contrast to PP and PSOE, which used Twitter/X more institutionally.

In this sense, it is also important to highlight that some studies have focused specifically on the way in which emerging parties use Twitter/X. Casero-Ripollés et al. (2017) also studied Podemos during the 2016 general elections and emphasized a complementary approach between the party and Pablo Iglesias.

According to the authors, Iglesias focused mainly on relating to the people and building his image through personal topics, while the party's Twitter account addressed more ideological and political aspects. Aladro-Vico & Requeijo-Rey (2020) examined Vox's online communication during the 2019 general elections and concluded that Vox uses "cult of law, nativism and closed group thinking" as its main strategies. Furthermore, the authors highlight how Vox's strategies encourage polarisation, at times adopting simplistic language and engaging in talks about a corrupt media ecosystem.

Overall, online political communication in Spain during elections appears to be rapidly developing. As Calvo et al. (2019) point out, different campaign teams in Spain have confirmed that they are using new tools and strategies based on data extraction and automated messages during the elections. In this new ecosystem, it is fundamental to consistently study the patterns of political communication and keep up to date on potential problems, including disinformation practices.

In relation to online disinformation campaigns during the Spanish elections, Paniagua-Rojano et al. (2020) examined 37 hoaxes identified by fact-checkers Maldita and Newtral during the 2019 general elections and concluded that the electoral system was the main target of disinformation narratives. According to the authors, most of these hoaxes warned people about rigged ballots that would result in votes being declared invalid. The most common type of hoax was the false attribution of actions. However, there were also cases where images were misattributed, photos were manipulated and in one case a political candidate was impersonated.

In the same election, Cano-Óron et al. (2021) examined disinformation in Facebook ads placed by political parties. The authors emphasize that while disinformation was unusual, it was not negligible. Moreover, it was mainly parties such as Ciudadanos and Vox that were behind the few ads that contained elements of disinformation.

On the other hand, disinformation was only found to a small extent in the PP ads and not at all in the PSOE and IU ads. In this sense, the authors believe that, as already mentioned by Lopez-Garcia et al. (2016) in relation to political communication, there is also a difference in disinformation practices between established and new parties.

With regard to the 2023 general elections, Maldita (2023) investigated the patterns of disinformation on social media platforms by analyzing 741 posts containing disinformation claims that were debunked in the course of the election. As in 2019 (Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020), the electoral process was again a target of disinformation, with one in four posts (24%) relating to this topic.

However, the authors highlight that this tendency increased to 40% in the week of the elections and 74% on the day of the elections, in a consolidated effort to discourage people from going to the polls. This time, postal voting was the main target of disinformation and not the ballot papers as in 2019.

Maldita (2023) also conducted an analysis of hate speech in disinformation posts and found that 32% of these posts met the criteria for hate speech. As mentioned by the authors, 78% of the hate speech was related to racist content and mainly targeted racialized people and migrants, accusing them of taking advantage of government welfare, committing crimes, and imposing their views on others.

Interestingly, Maldita (2023) also found that many of the disinformation narratives were amplified by political actors, which not only gave them greater reach but also enhanced their appearance of credibility. The authors conclude that PSOE, PP, Vox, and Sumar all contributed to the amplification of stories with disinformation elements.

In Spanish electoral processes, we find three main axes on which disinformation circulates: axis candidates and proposals, axis electoral campaigns, and axis institutions linked to the State.

Table 3. Main frameworks and narratives linked to electoral disinformation during general elections in Spain between 2019 and 2024

Axis Candidates and proposals	Axis electoral campaign	Axis: Institutions linked to the State
Fake images and videos.	Fake videos circulating on social media.	Disinformation related to public companies like Correos, Renfe, etc.
Deepfakes and slowed-down videos.	False statements and endorsements by international personalities, influencers, and celebrities.	Postal voting.
Possible party agreements.	False polls and information not published by the media.	Disinformation related to the act of voting.
Measures in case of governing.	Trolls, bots, and WhatsApp chains.	Disinformation about the vote counting process.
False statements and fake post or tweets.	False information related to rallies and/or demonstrations.	Overseas voting.
Candidates' links.	Non-political actors participating in campaigns: billboards, NGOs, etc.	Dissemination of false information about electoral legislation.
False electoral program content.	Consequences of the results (e.g., stock market crash).	

Source: Magallon-Rosa (2024). Edition: OberCom / SmartVote.

In the first case, we find fake images and videos, possible party agreements, measures in case of governing, etc. In the second axis, false statements and endorsements by international personalities, influencers, and celebrities, or false polls and information not published by the media.

Finally, the third axis is linked to the role of the State and public companies regarding postal voting or disinformation related to the act of voting or the vote counting process. In any case, the most significant trend is the rise of misinformation related to postal voting.

2.2.2. Portugal

In recent years, there has been an increase in studies in Portugal dealing with disinformation in elections. Rivas-de-Roca et al. emphasized in 2022 that electoral studies in Portugal tend to focus on traditional media, especially television, and that there are few studies dedicated to disinformation, especially in the online sphere.

However, this is gradually changing, particularly due to studies conducted by or in collaboration with MediaLab Iscte, dedicated to the study of online disinformation during elections (Cardoso et al., 2020; Casquinho et al., 2024a; Casquinho et al., 2024b; Vasconcelos et al., 2024; Cardoso & Moreno, 2025).

From a contextual perspective, general elections tend to receive more attention from citizens (Casquinho et al., 2024b), but also from academics (Rivas-de-Roca et al., 2022). The tendency for European elections to be seen as “second-order” (Reif & Schmitt, 1980) and to receive less attention overall also seems to be confirmed in Portugal (Freire & Santana-Pereira, 2018).

However, there are relatively more studies than in other European countries, mainly due to the intervention of Troika in the country in 2011, which, as Rivas-de-Roca et al. (2022) mention, appears to have contributed to an increase in studies (i.e. Magalhães, 2014; Freire & Santana-Pereira, 2018). In addition, since 2020, there appears to have been an increase in studies dealing with populism, the new far-right, and also disinformation (Figueira & Santos, 2019; Salgado et al., 2021; Baptista et al., 2021; Chamusca, 2024).

During electoral campaigns, citizens tend to behave differently depending on the social media platforms they use. On Facebook, content and news related to politics and elections are not very present, as topics such as sports, entertainment, and personalities receive the most attention (Casquinho et al., 2024a). Conversely, on Twitter/X, discussions about politics and elections are frequent, but tend to generate a low number of interactions (likes, comments, and shares) (Casquinho et al., 2024a).

It is important to understand that Twitter/X in Portugal has a relatively small number of users and tends to be used mainly by people interested in politics (Cardoso et al., 2024). Despite these differences, new actors such as political influencers have a growing relevance on both platforms (Casquinho et al., 2024a). Platforms such as TikTok and Instagram in particular are becoming increasingly important for the consumption of content related to political communication. From a quantitative perspective, media outlets tend to publish the most in social media, collecting a large number of interactions in some publications where political candidates are mentioned. Moreover, the periods with the most attention tend to coincide with television debates or when politicians appear in entertainment programs (Casquinho et al., 2024a & Casquinho et al., 2024b).

Regarding the activities of political candidates on social media during elections, Casquinho et al. (2024a; 2024b) highlight that posts with an emotional element tend to generate the most interactions, as well as posts related to their participation in entertainment programs. In addition, the authors emphasize that while Facebook and Twitter/X are the platforms on which political actors post the most, it is on Instagram that they gather the most interactions, showing the growing importance and relevance of this social media platform. In both the General and European elections in 2024, Chega, a conservative and populist right-wing political party currently led by André Ventura, distinguished itself by gathering the most interactions by large.

In terms of online disinformation in elections, corruption was identified as the main topic of false content on social media in 2019 (Cardoso et al., 2020; Baptista & Gradim, 2022). As Cardoso & Moreno (2025) note, narratives about corruption have long been used in Portugal with the intention of changing the current regime. In the 2019 elections, it was observed that while disinformation did not have a greater reach than real news, it was more likely to be shared (Baptista & Gradim, 2022). In addition, the main targets of these false narratives were the political left, especially the government and the then Prime Minister and current President of the European Council, António Costa (Cardoso et al., 2020; Baptista & Gradim, 2022).

It was also found that disinformation was mainly spread by accounts linked to the far-right of the political spectrum (Baptista & Gradim, 2022). Interestingly, studies also show that Portuguese individuals who identify as right-wing are more likely to believe in disinformation themselves, regardless of it being pro-left or pro-right (Baptista et al., 2021).

As Baptista & Gradim (2022) point out, false narratives about immigration were not prominent on social media at the time. In this sense, Portugal seemed to be an exception in Europe, where immigration was one of the main topics of disinformation approached by the far-right (Culloty & Suiter, 2021). According to Cardoso & Moreno (2025), Portugal was closer to Brazil than to Europe in terms of the narratives used to spread disinformation.

In 2024, when two elections took place in Portugal, the General Elections in March and the European elections in June, Casquinho et al. (2024a; 2024b), who analyzed disinformation on social media platforms during this period, noticed a change in the scenery. Starting in March, but intensifying in the midst of the European elections, it was found that immigration had become the main topic of disinformation, with content related to Islam in particular generating a very large number of interactions.

It is important to understand that while anti-immigration discourse has long been associated with right-wing populist political forces in Portugal, it is only recently that it has become a prominent topic that has been instrumentalized for disinformation purposes (Vasconcelos et al., 2024). Casquinho et al. (2024b) emphasize that immigration was the only consistent theme between Portugal and other European countries, while other themes, such as electoral fraud, Covid-19 and LGBTQ+, were not as relevant in the national context. They also point out that, just as in 2019, the far-right was still the biggest source of online disinformation.

Interestingly, Casquinho et al. (2024a; 2024b) also conclude that disinformation in Portugal usually requires some kind of “amplification” by political actors in order to spread effectively. In both the General and European elections, the authors found several cases that only became prominent on social media platforms after they had been exploited by political actors. Unlike in Spain, where several political forces were involved in these practices, the conclusion in Portugal was that André Ventura and the Chega party were generally the ones responsible for this amplification.

While immigration was the main topic of disinformation throughout 2024, corruption has recently become, once again, a relevant topic for disinformative narratives in Portugal (Cardoso & Moreno, 2025). The recent controversial events surrounding the now former Prime Minister Luís Montenegro and the start of the trial of former Prime Minister José Sócrates, on grounds of corruption, have revived the narrative of “all politicians being corrupt” on social media. Cardoso & Moreno (2025) conclude that the use of corruption or immigration as a disinformation topic depends on whether we are in the midst of General or European elections and on the overall media agenda.

2.2.3. Iberian outlook on disinformation trends

As we have seen in the previous sections, Portugal and Spain show both similarities and differences when it comes to online political communication and disinformation patterns during elections. If we focus on online discussions, it is clear that the overall progression is similar in both countries, with a clear increase in interest as the campaign progresses, especially during televised debates. (Marcos-García, 2016; Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020; Magallón-Rosa et al., 2019; Maldita, 2023; Casquinho et al., 2024a; Casquinho et al., 2024b). These are periods in which the volume of online discussions tends to increase significantly and therefore, we believe that it is essential to be especially cautious to prevent the spread of false narratives.

Despite the similar course of online discussions during elections, it is important to understand that Portugal and Spain have several historical and geographical characteristics that influence the studies conducted in both countries. For example, Spain, with its regional organisation, has a whole section of academic publications on online regional electoral communication (Magallón-Rosa et al., 2019; Calvo et al., 2019; Córdoba-Cabús et al., 2021; Rivas-de-Roca, 2021), that is not present in Portugal. On the other hand, Portugal, due to its difficult history with Troika, focuses more on the European elections (Magalhães, 2014; Freire & Santana-Pereira, 2018; Casquinho et al., 2024b), something that is not verified in Spain (Rivas-de-Roca, 2022).

In this sense, comparative analysis is fundamental to better understanding disinformation practices and to try to design coherent strategies to curb false narratives that address the specificities of both countries. In this context, we also believe it is important to highlight the work carried out in the Iberifier (Iberian Digital Media Observatory project). According to its website, “Iberifier is a digital media observatory for Spain and Portugal, supported by the European Commission and linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). Coordinated by the University of Navarra, it includes twelve universities, five fact-checking organizations and news agencies, and six multidisciplinary research centers”.

In particular, we recommend consulting the report pertaining to the “analysis of the impact of disinformation on political, economic, social and security issues, governance models and good practices: the cases of Spain and Portugal” (Badillo-Matos et al., 2023). In this report, the authors approach six case studies on disinformation in Portugal and Spain (3 for each country), including a case study on Covid-19 disinformation in each country.

Before approaching the patterns of online disinformation in elections, we consider it fundamental to present contextual comparative data between Portugal and Spain. Data from the 2024 Digital News Report shows that within a global sample, the most common disinformation topics that users believe to have come across are politics, Covid-19, economics (cost of living), and the Israel-Palestine conflict.

While Spain follows a similar distribution of topics, by importance – with significantly higher rates of people saying they have seen disinformation on immigrations and significantly lower ones when it comes to the War in Ukraine (Novoa-Jaso et al., 2024), Portugal stands out with much lower perception of disinformation regarding any of these topics. 28% claim to have encountered disinformation about politics last week, and the remaining topics were identified by about a fifth, or less, of the samples (Cardoso et al., 2024).

Table 4. Disinformation topics: "Have you seen false or misleading information about any of the following topics, in the last week?" (Multiple choice), Global, Portugal and Spain, 2024

	Global	Spain	Portugal
Politics	36%	37%	28%
Economics, cost of living	28%	28%	19%
Israel-Palestine conflict	27%	24%	19%
War in Ukraine	24%	16%	17%
Immigration	21%	27%	17%
Other health issues	18%	19%	15%
Coronavirus (Covid-19)	30%	29%	15%
Climate change or the environment	23%	23%	13%

Source: Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2024, Digital News Report España 2024 & Digital News Report Portugal 2024.
Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. nGlobal≈96.000, n≈2000 for Spain and Portugal.

However, as seen below, there are significant differences between both country samples and the younger 18-24 subsample, and even more so between younger men and younger women. In both countries, young men state in higher proportion to have encountered more disinformation on any of the topics, but that is particularly visible on politics and Covid-19 in Spain and on immigration, Coronavirus, and economics (cost of living) in Portugal.

In this sense, young women are much less prone to claim to have encountered disinformation content on topics such as the War in Ukraine, in Spain, and the Israel-Palestine conflict, War in Ukraine, and climate change, in Portugal.

Regarding online disinformation during elections in Portugal and Spain, it is clear that the parties/candidates currently in power or with a better chance of winning tend to be the biggest targets of disinformation. This was found to be the case in Spain (Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020; Maldita, 2023) and Portugal (Cardoso et al., 2020; Baptista & Gradim, 2020; Casquinho et al., 2024a).

However, while in Portugal the far-right was identified as the main source of disinformation (Baptista & Gradim, 2022; Cardoso et al., 2020; Casquinho et al., 2024a; Baptista et al., 2021), in Spain, Cano-Óron et al. (2021) concludes that political forces from different sides of the spectrum sometimes engage in these practices, especially those associated with emerging parties.

Table 5. Disinformation topics: "Have you seen false or misleading information about any of the following topics, in the last week? (Multiple choice) - Country samples and 18-24, Portugal and Spain, 2024

	Spain				Portugal			
	Spain	Spain 18-24	Spain Men 18-24's	Spain Women 18-24's	Portugal	Portugal 18-24's	Portugal Men 18-24's	Portugal Women 18-24's
Politics	37%	35%	40%	29%	28%	28%	31%	24%
Economics, cost of living	28%	25%	30%	19%	19%	19%	24%	14%
Israel-Palestine conflict	24%	26%	30%	21%	19%	15%	22%	8%
War in Ukraine	16%	15%	19%	10%	17%	15%	21%	8%
Immigration	27%	26%	32%	20%	17%	21%	25%	16%
Other health issues	19%	21%	22%	19%	17%	14%	16%	15%
Coronavirus (Covid-19)	29%	35%	42%	28%	15%	15%	24%	17%
Climate change or the environment	23%	23%	28%	18%	13%	14%	19%	7%

Source: Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2024, Digital News Report España 2024 & Digital News Report Portugal 2024. Edition: OberCom / SmartVote. nGlobal≈96.000, n≈2000 for Spain and Portugal.

In thematic terms, immigration has become an important topic of disinformation in Portugal since the 2024 European elections (Casquinho et al., 2024b). In Spain, the same was found in the 2023 general elections, with most hate speech in disinformation content targeting migrants, especially those whose religion is Islam (Maldita, 2023).

Nevertheless, it is important to emphasize that electoral fraud, which has been identified as a primary disinformation topic during elections in Spain (Paniagua-Rojano et al., 2020; Maldita, 2023), is not present in Portugal. Although corruption is an important disinformation topic in Portugal, it is directed against politicians (Cardoso et al., 2020; Casquinho et al., 2024a; Cardoso & Moreno, 2025) and not against the electoral system itself.

From a strategic perspective, it has been observed in both Spain and Portugal that disinformation in elections tends to be amplified by political actors, with this amplification giving visibility and credibility to disinformation content (Maldita, 2023; Casquinho et al., 2024a; Casquinho et al., 2024a). Overall, it appears that political parties choose to reinforce narratives that fit their agenda, regardless of whether they are true or false. While in Portugal, Casquinho et al. (2024a; 2024b) identified that the Chega party was usually behind this amplification.

in Spain, Maldita (2023) observed that several political forces engage in these practices. In this sense, Maldita (2023) directly emphasizes in their recommendations addressed to the government and political parties that political actors should be extremely careful not to partake in these practices.

In addition to the strategies employed, it is also important to highlight that in the last European elections, similarities were also found in terms of disinformative content used by political forces. In Figure 13., we can find two very similar publications utilized by Vox in Spain and Chega in Portugal, published on the same day, just a few hours apart.

In their work, Casquinho et al. (2024b) considered these publications decontextualized because they allude to a wave of Islamic migration and a general change in the legislation of European society that cannot be substantiated with factual data.

Figure 16. Instagram posts by Portugal's Chega party and Spain's Vox party on the Islamisation of Europe, 2024

Source: Casquinho, M., Vasconcelos, A., Moreno, J., Cardoso, G., Palma, N., Paisana, M., Pinto-Martinho, A. (2024a). Europeias 2024 - Amplificação do discurso político online e desinformação em Portugal. Publicações OberCom.

Previously, Belim (2020) had pointed out similarities between the online communication of Vox and Chega. Both parties present in-group favoritism to explore feelings of inclusion, with these types of posts receiving the most attention on social media (Belim, 2020).

These publications by Vox and Chega appear to have similar objectives. Overall, this consensus suggests that narratives are increasingly shared between countries, leading to cohesion at a European and international level. This factor, once again, underlines the importance of coordinated efforts to stop the spread of disinformation beyond national borders.

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